

THE SUCCESSFUL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TOURISM AND ACADEMIC MOBILITY (A MODEL FOR INCREASING THE DEMAND OF FOREIGN STUDENTS)ⁱ

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Abstract:

From the beginning of the tourism industry, he knew how to adapt himself to the needs of the citizen, the guest at the hotel, and the civil society. We are witnessing today of a growing variety in the tourism offerings in a large number of topics of life, from leisure tourism, sports and extreme tourism, corporate activities and medical tourism. The student mobility around the world creates for the "tourist space" a new world of business opportunity which is called, academic tourism.

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1. Introduction

In the recent years, there has been a marked trend of increasing the demand for academic mobility of academic students and researchers. Some say that this is part of a global phenomenon of population migration.

Since the Bologna reform, we have witnessed new terms such as international students, educational migration, and now the trend of academic tourism has also come. The number of international students, the European Union, and student movements in most countries of the world [1]. Student travel encourages exchange of ideas, contributes to education and plays an important role in greater international

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understanding. It also increases the interest in direct connection with the culture and social life of another country. From a conceptual point of view, academic mobility can be considered a type of tourism, since it meets the parameters used by international organizations related to tourism. Indeed, the activities of people who travel outside their usual environment for a period of less than a year, with a view to carrying out studies can be considered tourism [5].

The definition of tourism relates to the activities which offered by the host country for a non-local consumer audience that is interested or needs to stay within the country's borders for any purpose, for a period of less than one year. The UNWTO organization [6, p. 104] defined tourism as Tourism is the generic term to cover both demand and supply that has been adopted in various formats and used through the World.

Also, we find another definition, that the tourism is defined as the activities of persons identified as visitors. A visitor is someone who is making a visit to a main destination outside his / her usual environment for less than a year for any main purpose [including] holidays, leisure and recreation, business, health, education or other purposes. This scope is much wider than the traditional perception of tourists, which included only those traveling for leisure [2].

In previous years, employment sectors and organizations also found a connection between their field of knowledge and tourism, as evidenced by medical tourism, which is based on the Medical tourism reiterates to people traveling to a country other than their own to obtain medical treatment.

In the past, this is usually referred to those who traveled from less-developed countries to major medical centers in highly developed countries for treatment unavailable at home. However, in recent years it may equally refer to those from developed countries who travel to third-world countries for lower priced medical treatments. The motivation may be for medical services unavailable or illegal in the home country.

Hence, the Author fined a direct connection to the world of academic education. The academic mobility that creates movement of people for different periods to other countries (even under 12 months) can certainly meet the need for international cooperation and a significant contribution to the country hosting these students. Similar to tourist products provided to therapeutic tourism, or any other tourism group, it is possible to create "tourist products" that meet the academic need. Here are some of them [6]:

1. Accommodation and residential services for the period in which they study at the academic institution;

2. Transportation services to academic institutions, during leisure, vacations and holidays;
3. Medical insurance services;
4. Equipment rental;
5. Leisure activities for learning the area of study (guidance, recommendation of sites, discount at the entrance to sites);
6. Travel agencies to the mother country.

After the Bologna Reform, the country began to develop the business sector. It chose a number of cities with extensive academic activities, such as Valencia, Barcelona and Madrid, and began to operate a tourism system jointly with the academic institutions in each city [4]. After a short period of time, there was an increase in demand for the tourism "product" that was proposed, and the success was also reflected in an increase in the number of foreign students who arrived in that city. In this case, part of the success of increasing the demand for foreign students can be attributed to the tourist experience it underwent during the period.

For some reason, it appears that academic tourism is suitable only for short periods of study, such as the "academic experience" in the exchange of student delegations as ERASMUS programs, but it is also possible to develop academic tourism as a program suitable for "full studies". The role of the tourism establishment within the academic world is primarily in creating opportunities [5, p.92]. Many academic institutions are interested in attracting students, but they do not have the professional knowledge to create the extra value beyond the university faculties, such as quality teaching staff, laboratories and innovative curricula. Today, in a world of economic and global competition, the ability to attract students by creating additional value, such as familiarity with culture, academic and cultural experience, holding international conferences and building the university as a magnet for professionals, researchers and especially students is the most significant economic key [7].

2. What additional value can academic tourism bring?

Academic tourism can have a large number of uses. Starting with a "basket of services", that raises the name and the quality of the study period, and until marketing the university through a pre-built operational program.

Sketch No' 1 presents the advantages of academic tourism:

Source: Made by the Author from source [1,2,4]

Before developing the model, it is desirable to define the goals for building the model. What profit, and another value we would like to achieve from the construction of such a model. The author suggests that the model will be built to increase the demand for academic mobility of foreign students to the country. The main characteristics of the model are [2, p. 188]:

1. **Professional expertise in conferences** - The tourism system knows how to operate international conferences that respect the academic institution and enable it to have high international representation, thereby attracting professionals from academia.
2. **Cooperation with Municipalities** - In cities where there are academic institutions, there should be a common interest among all the factors that the city will benefit from the very hospitality of foreign students. The advantage and profit can be in the form of tourist infrastructure, improvement of "green" areas and sports areas, cultural centers, urban libraries, development of historical sites and religious sites (for religious students of the hosted students), hostels and hotels and a solution to employment problems.
3. **Marketing academic institutions in other countries** - Universities usually have no knowledge of how to contact potential students in other countries. Tourism

workers know how to approach target audiences and build a marketing profile similar to the sale of other tourism products such as hotel and site flights.

4. **Responding to the needs of the student** - The creation of a "basket of services" for the student who arrives for short periods of study experience as part of student exchange programs. During the course of studies, students are offered a variety of activities of tourism, trips, transportation, and knowledge of the country's culture.
5. **Linking international relations with other countries** - As part of international activity, it is appropriate to establish organizational and business ties with tourist offices in other countries and work together.

3. Conclusion

For the summery, the academic tourism model will contribute to increasing the attractiveness of the State and its services to foreign students who are examining the possibility of academic mobility. Through the Ministry of Tourism, it is possible to concentrate all the information required for the student and to become a type of address for him.

There is no doubt that in such a work mechanism, the student will experience a period of study that will leave him with a great feeling and satisfaction, both academically and emotionally, that will be the responsibility of the department that will handle academic tourism.

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